

THE (r_1, \dots, r_p) -BELL POLYNOMIALS

Mohammed Said Maamra

Faculty of Mathematics, RECITS's Laboratory, USTHB, Algiers, Algeria
mmaamra@usthb.dz or mmaamra@yahoo.fr

Miloud Mihoubi

Faculty of Mathematics, RECITS's laboratory,
USTHB, Algiers, Algeria.
mmihoubi@usthb.dz or miloudmihoubi@gmail.com

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Abstract

In a previous paper, Mihoubi et al. introduced the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Stirling numbers and the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Bell polynomials and gave some of their combinatorial and algebraic properties. These numbers and polynomials generalize, respectively, the r -Stirling numbers of the second kind introduced by Broder and the r -Bell polynomials introduced by Mező. In this paper, we prove that the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Stirling numbers of the second kind are log-concave. We also give generating functions and generalized recurrences related to the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Bell polynomials.

1. Introduction

In 1984, Broder [2] introduced and studied the r -Stirling number of the second kind $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_r$, which counts the number of partitions of the set $[n] = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ into k non-empty subsets such that the r first elements are in distinct subsets. In 2011, Mező [8] introduced and studied the r -Bell polynomials. In 2012, Mihoubi et al. [12] introduced and studied the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Stirling number of the second kind $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right\}_{r_1, \dots, r_p}$, which counts the number of partitions of the set $[n]$ into k non-empty subsets such that the elements of each of the p sets $R_1 := \{1, \dots, r_1\}$, $R_2 := \{r_1 + 1, \dots, r_1 + r_2\}$, \dots , $R_p := \{r_1 + \dots + r_{p-1} + 1, \dots, r_1 + \dots + r_p\}$ are in distinct subsets.

This work is motivated by the study of the r -Bell polynomials [8] and the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Stirling numbers of the second kind [12], in which we may establish

- the log-concavity of the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Stirling numbers of the second kind,
- generalized recurrences for the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Bell polynomials, and
- the ordinary generating functions of these numbers and polynomials.

To begin, by the symmetry of the (r_1, \dots, r_p) -Stirling numbers with respect to r_1, \dots, r_p , let us suppose that $r_1 \leq r_2 \leq \dots \leq r_p$, and throughout this paper we use the following notation and definitions

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_p &:= (r_1, \dots, r_p), \quad |\mathbf{r}_p| := r_1 + \dots + r_p, \\ P_t(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &:= (z + r_p)^t (z + r_p)^{r_1} \dots (z + r_p)^{r_{p-1}}, \quad t \in \mathbb{R}, \\ B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &:= \sum_{k=0}^{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} z^k, \quad n \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

and \mathbf{e}_i denotes the i -th vector of the canonical basis of \mathbb{R}^p . In [12], the following were proved:

$$B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_n(k; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{z^k}{k!}, \tag{1}$$

$$P_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \sum_{k=0}^{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} z^k. \tag{2}$$

For later use we define the following numbers

$$a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) = (-1)^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|-k} \sum_{|\mathbf{j}_{p-1}|=k} \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ j_1 \end{bmatrix} \dots \begin{bmatrix} r_{p-1} \\ j_{p-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad |\mathbf{j}_{p-1}| = j_1 + \dots + j_{p-1},$$

where $\begin{bmatrix} n \\ k \end{bmatrix}$ are the absolute Stirling numbers of the first kind. Upon using the known identity

$$(u)^r = \sum_{j=0}^r (-1)^{r-j} \begin{bmatrix} r \\ j \end{bmatrix} u^j$$

we may state that we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) u^k = (u)^{r_1} \dots (u)^{r_{p-1}}. \tag{3}$$

In our contribution, we give more properties for the \mathbf{r}_p -Stirling numbers and the \mathbf{r}_p -Bell polynomials. The paper is organized as follows. In the next section we prove

that the sequence $\left(\left\{\begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+r_p \end{matrix}\right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p}; 0 \leq k \leq n + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|\right)$ is strongly log-concave and we give an approximation of $\left\{\begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+r_p \end{matrix}\right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p}$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$ for a fixed k . In the third section we write $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ in the basis $\{B_{n+k}(z; r_p) : 0 \leq k \leq |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|\}$ and $B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ in the family of bases $\{z^j B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p) : 0 \leq j \leq n\}$. As consequences, we also give some identities for the \mathbf{r}_p -Stirling numbers. In the fourth section we give the ordinary generating functions of the \mathbf{r}_p -Stirling numbers of the second kind and the \mathbf{r}_p -Bell polynomials.

2. Log-Concavity of the \mathbf{r}_p -Stirling Numbers

In this section we discuss the real roots of the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$, the log-concavity of the sequence $\left(\left\{\begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+r_p \end{matrix}\right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p}, 0 \leq k \leq n + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|\right)$, the greatest maximizing index of $\left\{\begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix}\right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p}$ and we give an approximation of $\left\{\begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ m+r_p \end{matrix}\right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p}$ when n tends to infinity. The case $p = 1$ was studied by Mező [9] and another study is done by Zhao [15] for a large class of the Stirling numbers.

In what follows, for illustration or if the order of r_1, \dots, r_p is unknown, we write the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ as $B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_p)$ for which r_1, \dots, r_p are taken in any order.

Theorem 1. *The roots of the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ are real and non-positive.*

To prove this theorem, we use the following lemma.

Lemma 2. *Let j, p be nonnegative integers and set*

$$B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) := \exp(-z) \frac{d^j}{dz^j} (z^{r_p} \exp(z) B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)),$$

where $r_0 := 0$ and $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_0) := B_n(z) = \sum_{k=0}^n \left\{\begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix}\right\} z^k$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &= z^{r_p-j} B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_p, j) \quad \text{if } j < r_p, \\ B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &= B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_p, j) \quad \text{if } j \geq r_p, \end{aligned}$$

with $\deg B_n^{(j)} = n + |\mathbf{r}_p|$. In particular, we have $B_n^{(r_{p+1})}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_{p+1})$.

Proof. The definition of $B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ and the identity (1) show that we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \exp(z) B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \\ &= \frac{d^j}{dz^j} \left(\sum_{k \geq 0} P_n(k; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{z^{k+r_p}}{k!} \right) \\ &= \sum_{k \geq \max(0, j-r_p)} (k+r_p)^n (k+r_p)^{r_1} \cdots (k+r_p)^{r_{p-1}} (k+r_p)^j \frac{z^{k+r_p-j}}{k!}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, for $0 \leq j < r_p$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \exp(z) B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &= \sum_{k \geq 0} (k+r_p)^n (k+r_p)^{r_1} \cdots (k+r_p)^{r_{p-1}} (k+r_p)^j \frac{z^{k+r_p-j}}{k!} \\ &= z^{r_p-j} \exp(z) B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_p, j) \end{aligned}$$

and for $j \geq r_p$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \exp(z) B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &= \sum_{k \geq j-r_p} (k+r_p)^n (k+r_p)^{r_1} \cdots (k+r_p)^{r_{p-1}} (k+r_p)^j \frac{z^{k+r_p-j}}{k!} \\ &= \sum_{k \geq 0} (k+j)^n (k+j)^{r_1} \cdots (k+j)^{r_{p-1}} (k+j)^{r_p} \frac{z^k}{k!} \\ &= \exp(z) B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_p, j). \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that we have $\deg B_n^{(j)} = n + |\mathbf{r}_p|$ and for $j = r_{p+1} \geq r_p$ we obtain $B_n^{(r_{p+1})}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_p, r_{p+1}) = B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_{p+1})$. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. We will show by induction on p that the roots of the polynomials $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ are real and non-positive. Indeed, for $p = 0$ the classical Bell polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_0) = B_n(z)$ has only real non-positive roots and for $p = 1$ the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_1)$ is the r_1 -Bell polynomial introduced in [8] and has only real non-positive roots. Assume, for $1 \leq r_1 \leq r_2 \leq \dots \leq r_p$, that the roots of the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ are real and negative, denoted by $z_1, \dots, z_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|}$ with $0 > z_1 \geq \dots \geq z_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|}$. We will prove that the polynomial $B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ has only real non-positive roots and we conclude that the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_{p+1}) = B_n^{(r_{p+1})}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ (see Lemma 2) has only real non-positive roots.

Firstly, we examine the polynomials $B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ for $j < r_p$. Indeed, the above statements show that the function

$$f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) := \exp(z) B_n^{(0)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = z^{r_p} \exp(z) B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$$

vanishes at $z_0, z_1, \dots, z_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|}$ with $z_0 = 0 > z_1 \geq \dots \geq z_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|}$ and $z_0 = 0$ is of multiplicity r_p . Lemma 2 gives

$$\frac{d}{dz} (f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)) = \exp(z) B_n^{(1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = z^{r_p-1} \exp(z) B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_{p-1}, r_p, 1)$$

and by applying Rolle's theorem to the function $f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ we conclude that its derivative $\frac{d}{dz} (f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p))$ vanishes at some points $x_1, \dots, x_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|}$ with $0 > x_1 \geq z_1 \geq x_2 \geq \dots \geq x_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \geq z_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|}$. Consequently, the polynomial $B_n^{(1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ vanishes at $x_1, \dots, x_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|}$ and at $x_0 = 0$ (with multiplicity $r_p - 1$). The number of these roots is $(n + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|) + (r_p - 1) = n + |\mathbf{r}_p| - 1$. Because $B_n^{(1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ is of degree $n + |\mathbf{r}_p|$ (see Lemma 2), it must have exactly $n + |\mathbf{r}_p|$ finite roots; the missing one, denoted by $x_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|+1}$, cannot be complex. By the fact that the coefficients of z^k in $B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_{p-1}, r_p, 1)$ are positive, the root $x_{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|+1}$ must be negative too. So, the polynomial $B_n^{(1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ has $n + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}| + 1$ real negative roots and $z = 0$ is a root with multiplicity $r_p - 1$. Similarly, we apply Rolle's theorem to the function $\frac{d}{dz} (f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p))$ to conclude that the polynomial $B_n^{(2)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ has $n + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}| + 2$ real negative roots and $z = 0$ is a root with multiplicity $r_p - 2$, and so on. So, the polynomials $B_n^{(0)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p), B_n^{(1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p), \dots, B_n^{(r_p-1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ have only real non-positive roots.

Secondly, we examine the polynomials $B_n^{(j)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ for $r_p \leq j \leq r_{p+1}$. Indeed, we have $B_n^{(r_p)}(0; \mathbf{r}_p) \neq 0$ and consider the function

$$\frac{d^{r_p-1}}{dz^{r_p-1}} f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \exp(z) B_n^{(r_p-1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = z \exp(z) B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_{p-1}, r_p, r_{p-1}).$$

As it is shown above, this function has $n + |\mathbf{r}_p| - 1$ real negative roots and the root $z = 0$, then Rolle's theorem shows that its derivative

$$\frac{d^{r_p}}{dz^{r_p}} f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \exp(z) B_n^{(r_p)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \exp(z) B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_{p-1}, r_p, r_p)$$

has at least $n + |\mathbf{r}_p| - 1$ real negative roots. This means that the polynomial

$$B_n^{(r_p)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_{p-1}, r_p, r_p)$$

has at least $n + |\mathbf{r}_p| - 1$ real negative roots and because it is of degree $n + |\mathbf{r}_p|$, the missing one cannot be complex. By the fact that the coefficients of z^k in $B_n(z; r_1, \dots, r_{p-1}, r_p, r_p)$ are positive, this root must be negative too. So, the polynomial $B_n^{(r_p)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ has $n + |\mathbf{r}_p|$ real negative roots. Similarly, apply Rolle's theorem to $\frac{d^{r_p}}{dz^{r_p}} f_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ and conclude that the polynomial $B_n^{(r_p+1)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ has $n + |\mathbf{r}_p|$ real negative roots and so on. So, the polynomials $B_n^{(r_p)}(z; \mathbf{r}_p), \dots, B_n^{(r_{p+1})}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ vanish only at negative numbers. Then, the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_{p+1}) = B_n^{(r_{p+1})}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ (see Lemma 2) has only real negative roots. \square

Upon using Newton’s inequality [6, p. 52], which is given by

Theorem 3. (*Newton’s inequality*) Let a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n be real numbers. If all the zeros of the polynomial $P(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_k x^k$ are real, then the coefficients of P satisfy

$$a_i^2 \geq \left(1 + \frac{1}{i}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{n-i}\right) a_{i+1} a_{i-1}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1,$$

we may state that:

Corollary 4. The sequence $\left\{ \binom{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|}{k+r_p}_{\mathbf{r}_p}, 0 \leq k \leq n + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}| \right\}$ is strongly log-concave (and thus unimodal).

This property shows that the sequence $(\binom{n}{k}_{\mathbf{r}_p}, 0 \leq k \leq n)$ admits an index $K \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$ for which $\binom{n}{K}_{\mathbf{r}_p}$ is the maximum of $\binom{n}{k}_{\mathbf{r}_p}$. An application of Darroch’s inequality [3] will help us to localize this index.

Theorem 5. (*Darroch’s inequality*) Let a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n be real numbers. If all the zeros of the polynomial $P(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_k x^k$ are real and negative and $P(1) > 0$, then the value of k for which a_k is maximized is within one of $P'(1)/P(1)$.

The following corollary gives a small interval for this index.

Corollary 6. Let K_{n,\mathbf{r}_p} be the greatest maximizing index of $\binom{n}{k}_{\mathbf{r}_p}$. We have

$$\left| K_{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|,\mathbf{r}_p} - \left(\frac{B_{n+1}(1; \mathbf{r}_p)}{B_n(1; \mathbf{r}_p)} - (r_p + 1) \right) \right| < 1.$$

Proof. Since the sequence $\left\{ \binom{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|}{k+r_p}_{\mathbf{r}_p} \right\}$ is strongly log-concave, there exists an index $K_{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|,\mathbf{r}_p}$ for which $\binom{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|}{r_p}_{\mathbf{r}_p} < \dots < \binom{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|}{K_{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|,\mathbf{r}_p}}_{\mathbf{r}_p} > \dots > \binom{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|}{n+r_p}_{\mathbf{r}_p}$. Then, on applying Theorem 1 and Darroch’s theorem, we obtain

$$\left| K_{n+|\mathbf{r}_p|,\mathbf{r}_p} - \frac{\frac{d}{dz} B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \Big|_{z=1}}{B_n(1; \mathbf{r}_p)} \right| < 1.$$

It remains to use the first identity given in [12, Corollary 12] by $z \frac{d}{dz} (B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)) = B_{n+1}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) - (z + r_p) B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$. □

3. Generalized Recurrences and Consequences

In this section, different representations of the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ in different bases or families of basis are given by Theorems 7 and 10. Indeed, a representation in the basis $\{B_{n+k}(z; r_p) : 0 \leq k \leq n + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|\}$ is given by the following theorem.

Theorem 7. *We have*

$$B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) B_{n+k}(z; r_p),$$

$$B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_{p+q}) = \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) B_{n+k}(z; r_p, \dots, r_{p+q}).$$

Proof. Upon using the fact that $(k + r_p)^{r_m} = \sum_{j=0}^{r_m} (-1)^{r_m-j} \begin{bmatrix} r_m \\ j \end{bmatrix} (k + r_p)^j$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &= \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_n(k; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{z^k}{k!} \\ &= \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} \sum_{j=0}^{r_m} (-1)^{r_m-j} \begin{bmatrix} r_m \\ j \end{bmatrix} \frac{P_0(k; \mathbf{r}_p)}{(k + r_p)^{r_m}} (k + r_p)^{n+j} \frac{z^k}{k!} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{r_m} (-1)^{r_m-j} \begin{bmatrix} r_m \\ j \end{bmatrix} B_{n+j}(z; \mathbf{r}_p - r_m \mathbf{e}_m), \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, p-1, \end{aligned}$$

and with the same process, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &= \sum_{j_1=0}^{r_1} \dots \sum_{j_{p-1}=0}^{r_{p-1}} (-1)^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}| - |\mathbf{j}_{p-1}|} \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ j_1 \end{bmatrix} \dots \begin{bmatrix} r_{p-1} \\ j_{p-1} \end{bmatrix} B_{n+|\mathbf{j}_{p-1}|}(z; r_p) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} (-1)^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}| - k} B_{n+k}(z; r_p) \sum_{|\mathbf{j}_{p-1}|=k} \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ j_1 \end{bmatrix} \dots \begin{bmatrix} r_{p-1} \\ j_{p-1} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) B_{n+k}(z; r_p). \end{aligned}$$

This implies the first identity of the theorem.

Now, from Lemma 2 we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \exp(-z) \frac{d^{r_{p+1}}}{dz^{r_{p+1}}} (z^{r_p} \exp(z) B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)) \\ = \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) \exp(-z) \frac{d^{r_{p+1}}}{dz^{r_{p+1}}} (z^{r_p} \exp(z) B_{n+k}(z; r_p)), \end{aligned}$$

which gives by utilizing Lemma 2: $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_{p+1}) = \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) B_{n+k}(z; r_p, r_{p+1})$.
 We can repeat this process q times to obtain the second identity of the theorem. \square

So, the \mathbf{r}_p -Stirling numbers admit an expression in terms of the usual r -Stirling numbers given by the following corollary.

Corollary 8. *We have*

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} n + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} = \sum_{j=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + j + r_p \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} a_j(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}).$$

Proof. Using Theorem 7, the polynomial $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_j(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) B_{n+j}(z; r_p) &= \sum_{j=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_j(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) \sum_{k=0}^{n+j} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + j + r_p \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} z^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} z^k \sum_{j=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_j(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + j + r_p \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} \end{aligned}$$

and since $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \sum_{k=0}^{n+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} z^k$, the identity follows by identification. \square

In [12], we proved the following:

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{t^n}{n!} = B_0(z \exp(t); \mathbf{r}_p) \exp(z(\exp(t) - 1) + r_p t).$$

The following theorem gives more details on the exponential generating function of the \mathbf{r}_p -Bell polynomials and will be used later.

Theorem 9. *We have*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{t^n}{n!} &= B_m(z \exp(t); \mathbf{r}_p) \exp(z(\exp(t) - 1) + r_p t) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) \frac{d^{m+k}}{dt^{m+k}} (\exp(z(\exp(t) - 1) + r_p t)). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Use (1) to get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{t^n}{n!} &= \sum_{n \geq 0} \left(\exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_0(k; \mathbf{r}_p) (k + r_p)^{n+m} \frac{z^k}{k!} \right) \frac{t^n}{n!} \\ &= \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_0(k; \mathbf{r}_p) (k + r_p)^m \frac{z^k \exp((k + r_p)t)}{k!} \\ &= B_m(z \exp(t); \mathbf{r}_p) \exp(z(\exp(t) - 1) + r_p t). \end{aligned}$$

For the second part of the theorem, use Theorem 7 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{t^n}{n!} &= \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{n+m+k}(z; r_p) \frac{t^n}{n!} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) \frac{d^{m+k}}{dt^{m+k}} \left(\sum_{n \geq 0} B_n(z; r_p) \frac{t^n}{n!} \right) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_k(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) \frac{d^{m+k}}{dt^{m+k}} (\exp(z(\exp(t) - 1) + r_p t)). \end{aligned}$$

□

Using combinatorial arguments, Spivey [13] established the following identity:

$$B_{n+m} = \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^m \left\{ \begin{matrix} m \\ j \end{matrix} \right\} \binom{n}{k} j^{n-k} B_k,$$

where B_n is the n -th Bell number, i.e., the number of ways to partition a set of n elements into non-empty subsets. After that, Belbachir et al. [1] and Gould et al. [7] showed, using different methods, that the polynomial $B_{n+m}(z) = B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{0})$ admits a recurrence relation related to the family $\{z^i B_j(z)\}$ as follows:

$$B_{n+m}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^m \left\{ \begin{matrix} m \\ j \end{matrix} \right\} \binom{n}{k} j^{n-k} z^j B_k(z). \tag{4}$$

Recently, Xu [14] gave a recurrence relation on a large family of Stirling numbers and Mihoubi et al. [11] extended the relation (4) to r -Bell polynomials as follows:

$$B_{n+m,r}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^m \left\{ \begin{matrix} m+r \\ j+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r \binom{n}{k} j^{n-k} x^j B_{k,r}(x). \tag{5}$$

Other recurrence relations are given by Mező [10]. The following theorem generalizes the Identities (4) and (5), and the Carlitz's identities [4, 5] given by

$$B_{n+m}(1; r) = \sum_{k=0}^m \left\{ \begin{matrix} m+r \\ k+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r B_n(1; k+r),$$

$$B_n(1; r+s) = \sum_{k=0}^s \left[\begin{matrix} s+r \\ k+r \end{matrix} \right]_r (-1)^{s-k} B_{n+k}(1; r),$$

and shows that $B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ admits r -Stirling recurrence coefficients in the families of basis

$$\{z^j B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p) : 0 \leq j \leq n\},$$

$$\{z^j B_{m+i}(z; r+j) : 0 \leq i \leq |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|, 0 \leq j \leq n\},$$

where $B_n(1; r)$ is the number of ways to partition a set of n elements into non-empty subsets such that the r first elements are in different subsets.

Theorem 10. *We have*

$$B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} z^j B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p),$$

$$B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \sum_{i=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} a_i(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) z^j B_{m+i}(z; r_p + j),$$

$$z^n B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + n\mathbf{e}_p) = \sum_{j=0}^n \left[\begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{matrix} \right]_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} B_{m+j}(z; \mathbf{r}_p).$$

Proof. Let $T_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p) := \sum_{n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} z^j B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p) \right) \frac{t^n}{n!}$. The second identity given in [12, Corollary 12] by

$$\exp(z) B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + \mathbf{e}_p) = \frac{d}{dz} (\exp(z) B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p))$$

can be used to get

$$\exp(z) B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p) = \frac{d^j}{dz^j} (\exp(z) B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p)). \tag{6}$$

Identity (6) and the exponential generating function of the r -Stirling numbers (see [2])

$$\sum_{n \geq j} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} \frac{t^n}{n!} = \frac{1}{j!} (\exp(t) - 1)^j \exp(r_p t)$$

prove that

$$\begin{aligned} T_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p) &= \sum_{j \geq 0} B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p) z^j \frac{1}{j!} (\exp(t) - 1)^j \exp(r_p t) \\ &= \exp(r_p t - z) \sum_{j \geq 0} \frac{d^j}{dz^j} (\exp(z) B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p)) \frac{(z(\exp(t) - 1))^j}{j!}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, by the Taylor-Maclaurin expansion we have

$$\sum_{j \geq 0} \frac{d^j}{dz^j} (\exp(z) B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p)) \frac{(u - z)^j}{j!} = \exp(u) B_m(u; \mathbf{r}_p).$$

So, this identity and Theorem 9 show that we have

$$T_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \exp(r_p t - z) \exp(z \exp(t)) B_m(z \exp(t); \mathbf{r}_p) = \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{t^n}{n!}.$$

By comparing the coefficients of t^n in the two expressions of $T_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$, the first identity of this theorem follows. The second identity follows by replacing $B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p)$, as given by its expression in Theorem 7 by

$$\sum_{i=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_i(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) B_{m+i}(z; j + r_p).$$

For the third identity, let $A := \sum_{j=0}^n \begin{bmatrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{bmatrix}_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} B_{m+j}(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$. We use Identity (1) and the known identity $(k + r_p)^n = \sum_{j=0}^n \begin{bmatrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{bmatrix}_{r_p} k^j$ (see [2]) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_m(k; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{z^k}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^n \begin{bmatrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{bmatrix}_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} (k+r_p)^j \\ &= (-1)^n \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_m(k; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{z^k}{k!} \sum_{j=0}^n \begin{bmatrix} n+r_p \\ j+r_p \end{bmatrix}_{r_p} (-k-r_p)^j \\ &= (-1)^n \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_m(k; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{z^k}{k!} (-k-r_p+r_p)^n \\ &= \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq n} P_m(k; \mathbf{r}_p) k^n \frac{z^k}{k!} \\ &= z^n \exp(-z) \sum_{k \geq 0} P_m(k+n; \mathbf{r}_p) \frac{z^k}{k!} \\ &= z^n B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + n\mathbf{e}_p). \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

As consequences of Theorem 10, some identities for the \mathbf{r}_p -Stirling numbers of the second kind can be deduced as is shown by the following corollary.

Corollary 11. *We have*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=0}^k \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ i + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ k - i + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} = \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + m + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p}, \\ & \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + j + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + n + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} \left[\begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right]_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} = \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + |\mathbf{r}_p| + n \\ k + r_p + n \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p + n\mathbf{e}_p}, \\ & \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + j + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} \left[\begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right]_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} = 0, \quad k < n. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From the first identity of Theorem 10 we have

$$B_{n+m}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) = \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} z^j B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + j\mathbf{e}_p)$$

which can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{n+m+|\mathbf{r}_p-1|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + m + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} z^k &= \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p} z^j \sum_{i=0}^{m+|\mathbf{r}_p-1|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ i + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} z^i \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n+m+|\mathbf{r}_p-1|} z^k \sum_{i=0}^k \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ i + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ k - i + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{r_p}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, the desired identity follows by comparing the coefficients of z^k in the last expansion. Using the definition of $B_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ and the third identity of Theorem 10, the second and the third identities of the corollary follow from the definition

$$B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + n\mathbf{e}_p) = \sum_{k=0}^{m+|\mathbf{r}_p-1|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + |\mathbf{r}_p| + n \\ k + r_p + n \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p + n\mathbf{e}_p} z^k$$

and the expansion

$$\begin{aligned} B_m(z; \mathbf{r}_p + n\mathbf{e}_p) &= z^{-n} \sum_{j=0}^n \left[\begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right]_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} B_{m+j}(z; \mathbf{r}_p) \\ &= z^{-n} \sum_{j=0}^n \left[\begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right]_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} \sum_{k=0}^{m+j+|\mathbf{r}_p-1|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + j + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} z^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{m+n+|\mathbf{r}_p-1|} z^{k-n} \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + j + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} \left[\begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right]_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j} \\ &= \sum_{k=-n}^{m+|\mathbf{r}_p-1|} z^k \sum_{j=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} m + j + |\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k + n + r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} \left[\begin{matrix} n + r_p \\ j + r_p \end{matrix} \right]_{r_p} (-1)^{n-j}. \end{aligned}$$

□

4. Ordinary Generating Functions

The *ordinary generating function* of the r -Stirling numbers of the second kind [2] is given by

$$\sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r \\ k+r \end{matrix} \right\}_r t^n = t^k \prod_{j=0}^k (1 - (r+j)t)^{-1}. \tag{7}$$

An analogous result for the \mathbf{r}_p -Stirling numbers is given by the following theorem.

Theorem 12. *Let*

$$\tilde{B}_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) := \sum_{k=0}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_p| \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} z^k.$$

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_p| \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} t^n &= t^{k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{r_1} \cdots \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{r_{p-1}} \prod_{j=0}^{k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} (1 - (r_p + j)t)^{-1}, \\ \sum_{n \geq 0} \tilde{B}_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p) t^n &= \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{r_1} \cdots \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{r_{p-1}} \sum_{k \geq |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \frac{z^{k-|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} t^k}{\prod_{j=0}^k (1 - (r_p + j)t)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Use Corollary 8 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_p| \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} t^n &= \sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} t^n \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_j(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) t^{-j} \sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+j+r_p \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} t^{n+j} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_j(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) t^{-j} \sum_{n \geq k+j} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} t^n, \end{aligned}$$

and because $\left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} = 0$ for $n = k, \dots, k + |\mathbf{r}_{p-1}| - 1$, we get

$$\sum_{n \geq k} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+|\mathbf{r}_p| \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_p| \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} t^n = \left(\sum_{n \geq k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+r_p \\ k+|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|+r_p \end{matrix} \right\}_{\mathbf{r}_p} t^n \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^{|\mathbf{r}_{p-1}|} a_j(\mathbf{r}_{p-1}) t^{-j} \right).$$

The first generating function of the theorem follows by using (3) and (7). For the second one, use the definition of $\tilde{B}_n(z; \mathbf{r}_p)$ and the last expansion. \square

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